

Studies on 4, 4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl Methane

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4,4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl methane with ethyl acetoacetate gave bi(4-methyl-6-coumarinyl) methane. The benzoyl derivative of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy-diphenyl methane gave a methylene bis (β -diketone) on Baker-Venkataraman transformation which was cyclised to bi (6-flavonyl)methane. The above hydroxy acetyl derivative gave bi(4-hydroxy-6-coumarinyl) methane with ethyl carbonate. Bi(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl) methane is also synthesised from the diacetyl derivative.

4,4'-Didihydroxydiphenyl methane did not give a pure product on chloromethylation but its dimethyl ether gave the 3,3'-di(chloromethyl) derivative which has been converted into the diacetoxyethyl and the di(cyanomethyl) derivatives and into the diformyl derivative.

3,3'-Diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane was condensed with diethyl bromo malonate and bi(5-benzofuranyl) methane was synthesised. Bi(3-carbethoxy-6-coumarinyl) methane was obtained on condensation of the diformyl derivative with diethyl malonate. This on hydrolysis and decarboxylation gave bi(6-coumarinyl) methane which was also obtained by Perkin acetylation of 3,3'-diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxy-diphenyl methane.

In continuation of the work done on 4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl¹ and 4,4'-dihydroxy-benzophenone², some studies have now been made on 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane and several oxygen heterocycles have been synthesised.

4,4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl methane³ on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of 80% sulphuric acid gave a product which has been assigned the bi(4-methyl-6-coumarinyl) methane (I) structure. That it is a coumarin derivative was proved by its

conversion into a methylene bis(cinnamic acid) derivative by heating it in acetone solution with potassium hydroxide and dimethyl sulphate. 4,4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl methane did not condense with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of either phosphorus pentoxide or anhydrous aluminium chloride as the condensing agent or when the reactants were refluxed in diphenyl ether without the use of any condensing agent.

For the synthesis of bi(6-flavonyl)methane, the required intermediate, 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane was synthesised through the Fries migration of 4,4'-diacetyldiphenyl methane. Its structure was established by oxidising its dimethyl ether with alkaline potassium permanganate to the known 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone-3,3'-dicarboxylic acid^{2,4}.

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane was converted into its dibenzoyloxy derivative. This on Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement gave a methylene bis β -diketone which on cyclisation gave bi(6-flavonyl)methane (VI). The synthesis of bi(3-methyl-5-benzofuranyl)methane has been achieved by condensing 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane with ethyl bromoacetate. The 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-di(carbethoxymethoxy) diphenyl methane obtained was hydrolysed to the corresponding dicarboxylic acid. This was then treated with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride when through simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation the desired benzofuran derivative (IV) was obtained. 3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy-diphenyl methane when treated with ethyl carbonate in the presence of pulverised sodium gave bi(4-hydroxy-6-coumarinyl)methane (II).

The chloromethylation of 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane did not give a pure product but the chloromethylation of its dimethyl ether gave a pure 3,3'-di(chloromethyl) derivative. On alkaline potassium permanganate oxidation it gave the known 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone-3,3'-dicarboxylic acid² as seen by direct comparison. The di(chloromethyl) derivative has been converted into the diacetoxy derivative by reacting with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride and into the 3,3'-di(cyanomethyl) derivative by treatment with potassium cyanide. The latter has been hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid to the corresponding 3,3'-di(carboxymethyl) derivative. The 3,3'-di(chloromethyl) derivative on Sommelet reaction gave the 3,3'-diformyl derivative. On demethylation it gave 3,3'-diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane, previously prepared by Marvel and Tarkoy⁵ by the direct condensation of salicylaldehyde with trioxan.

3,3'-Diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane on condensation with diethyl bromomalonate gave bi(2-carbethoxy-5-benzofuranyl)methane which was hydrolysed to the corresponding dicarboxylic acid which on heating with quinoline and copper powder gave bi(5-benzofuranyl) methane (V). 3,3'-Diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane on condensation with ethyl malonate in the presence of piperidine gave bi(3-carbethoxy-6-coumarinyl) methane which on hydrolysis and decarboxylation gave bi(-6-coumarinyl) methane (III) which was also obtained directly by the Perkin acetylation of 3,3'-diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bi(4-methyl-6-coumarinyl)methane: A mixture of 4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane³ (2 g.), ethylacetoacetate (4 ml.) and sulphuric acid (80%; 15 ml.) was kept for 24 hr. It was

then poured on crushed ice and the separated product after treatment with alkali was crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Yield 0.5 g, m.p. 282–84°. (Found : C, 75.71; H, 4.64. $C_{21}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 75.89; H, 4.85%).

Bi(β -Methyl-2-methoxy-5-cinnamyl)methane : The above coumarin (0.2 g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide (20%; 5 ml.), dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) and acetone (20 ml.) for 4 hr. The product obtained on acidification of the alkaline solution was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white granules, m.p. 178–79°. It decolourised bromine water and potassium permanganate solution. (Found : C, 69.95; H, 5.97. $C_{23}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 69.70; H, 6.06%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane : A mixture of 4,4'-diacetoxy diphenyl methane (1 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 130–40° for 1 hr. It was decomposed with ice cold hydrochloric acid and the product was taken up in sodium hydroxide solution. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from alcohol in brown needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 155°. It gave a brownish green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 71.83; H, 5.55. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.82; H, 5.63%).

The di(2,4-DNP) : Prepared from the above compound with 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrazine in alcohol was crystallised from diphenyl ether in orange shining needles, m.p. 291° (decomp.). (Found : N, 17.66. $C_{29}H_{24}O_{10}N_8$ requires N, 17.40%).

The dimethyl ether : Prepared by refluxing a mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane (1 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) in dry acetone for 16 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone and adding water was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in white shining plates (0.8 g.), m.p. 71–72°. (Found : C, 73.14; H, 6.13. $C_{19}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 73.06; H, 6.41%).

4,4'-Dimethoxy-benzophenone-3,3'-dicarboxylic acid was obtained by refluxing a mixture of the above dimethylether (0.5 g.), potassium permanganate (2 g.) and potassium hydroxide solution (10%; 15 ml.) for 8 hr. More of potassium permanganate (1 g.) was added in small quantity at regular intervals and the product obtained on acidification was crystallised from alcohol in light needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 245°. Ishiwata and Takada⁴ reported m.p. 242–43°. Balani and Sethua² reported m.p. 242°.

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dibenzoyloxy diphenyl methane : Prepared from 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane with benzoyl chloride in the presence of pyridine and crystallised from alcohol in white shining needles, m.p. 123–24°. (Found : C, 75.82; H, 4.83. $C_{31}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 75.60; H, 4.88%).

3,3'-Di(benzoylacetyl)4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane : A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dibenzoyloxy diphenyl methane (0.5 g.), crushed potassium hydroxide (3 g.) and pyridine (5 ml.) was kept for 4 hr. at room temperature. Ice cold hydrochloric acid was added to the above reaction mixture. The separated product was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow granules (0.2 g.), m.p. 182–83°. It gave brownish green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 75.53; H, 4.97. $C_{31}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 75.60; H, 4.88%).

Bi(6-flavonyl)methane : The above β -diketone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) and con. sulphuric acid (2 drops) for 4 hr. The separated product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in white shining plates (0.4 g.). It was insoluble in alkali, m.p. 253–54°. It gave light violet fluorescence with con. sulphuric acid. (Found : C, 81.51; H, 4.34. $C_{31}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 81.55; H, 4.39%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-di(carbethoxymethoxy) diphenyl methane : A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane (1 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (2 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone for 16 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in white shining leaflets (1 g.), m.p. 126°. (Found : C, 65.64; H, 6.11. $C_{25}H_{28}O_8$ requires C, 65.78; H, 6.18%).

3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-di(carboxymethoxy)diphenyl methane : The above ester (1 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (20 ml.; 10%) for 1 hr. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from dil. alcohol in white shining needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 201–2°. (Found : C, 63.49; H, 5.00. $C_{21}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 63.30; H, 5.03%).

Bi(3-Methyl-5-benzofuranyl)methane : The above acid (1 g.) was refluxed with sodium acetate (4 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.) for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into water. The separated product was crystallised from alcohol in white granules (0.5 g.), m.p. 102–3°. (Found : C, 82.47; H, 5.59. $C_{19}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 82.60; H, 5.79%).

Bi(4-Hydroxy-6-coumarinyl)methane : A mixture of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane (1 g.), ethyl carbonate (25 ml.) and pulverised sodium (3 g.) was refluxed for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into water and the product obtained on acidification was crystallised from nitrobenzene. Yield 0.5 g., m.p. 296°. (Found : C, 67.45; H, 3.44. $C_{19}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 67.86; H, 3.57%).

3,3'-Di(chloromethyl)4,4'-dimethoxy diphenyl methane : On passing hydrochloric acid gas through a clear mixture of 4,4'-dimethoxy diphenyl methane (2 g.), paraformaldehyde (2 g.) and acetic acid (20 ml., 90%) for 3 hr. 3,3'-Di(chloromethyl) derivative separated. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in white shining cubes (0.8 g.), m.p. 114–15°. (Found : C, 62.55; H, 5.20; Cl, 21.88. $C_{17}H_{18}Cl_2O_2$ requires C, 62.76; H, 5.54; Cl, 21.85%).

The above di(chloromethyl) derivative (0.5 g.) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (20 ml.; 10%), and potassium permanganate (2 g.) on a wire gauze for 6 hr. On working up as usual, it gave, 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone-3,3'-dicarboxylic acid described earlier.

The di(acetoxymethyl) derivative : The above di(chloromethyl) derivative (0.5 g.) was refluxed with fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) for 1 hr. The product obtained on dilution with water was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in white buds (0.3 g.), m.p. 72–73°. (Found : C, 68.10; H, 6.28. $C_{21}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 67.74; H, 6.45%).

The di(cyanomethyl) derivative : The di(chloromethyl) derivative (1 g.) was refluxed with potassium cyanide (1 g.) and sodium iodide (0.2 g.) in dry acetone for 20 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone and washing with water was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in white needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 122–23°. (Found : C, 74.49; H, 5.77; N, 9.10. $C_{19}H_{18}N_2O_2$ requires C, 74.50; H, 5.88; N, 9.15%).

3,3'-Di(carboxymethyl)-4,4'-dimethoxy diphenyl methane : The above di(cyanomethyl) derivative (0.5 g.) was refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml.) for 6 hr. The separated acid was crystallised from dil. alcohol in pale yellow needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 173°. (Found : C, 66.01; H, 5.64. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 66.26; H, 5.81%).

3,3'-Diformyl-4,4'-dimethoxy diphenyl methane : A mixture of the di(chloromethyl) derivative (1 g.), hexamine (3 g.) and chloroform (20 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 5 hr. The separated complex was refluxed with acetic acid (50%; 20 ml.) for 3 hr. The product obtained on dilution of acetic acid was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in white buds (0.5 g.), m.p. 135°. (Found : C, 71.78; H, 5.43. $C_{17}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 71.83; H, 5.63%).

The di(2,4-DNP) was prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene in orange needles, m.p. 282°. (Found : N, 17.07%. $C_{29}H_{24}N_8O_{10}$ requires N, 17.39%).

Demethylation : 3,3'-Diformyl-4,4'-dimethoxy diphenyl methane (1 g.) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) in nitrobenzene (5 ml.) and heated in an oil bath at 110° for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice cold hydrochloric acid and the nitrobenzene removed by steam distillation. The 3,3'-diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane obtained was crystallised from dil. acetic acid in pale yellow shining needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 143°. Marvel and Tarkoy⁵ give the same m.p. It gave a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 70.62; H, 4.58. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.31; H, 4.69%).

Bi(2-carbethoxy-5-benzofuranyl)methane : 3,3'-Diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane (1 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromomalonate (2 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) in dry ethyl methyl ketone (25 ml.) on a steam bath for 14 hr. The solvent was removed and water was added. The product obtained was crystallised from alcohol in white needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 134°. (Found : C, 70.65; H, 5.28. $C_{23}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 70.40; H, 5.10%).

Bi(2-carboxy-5-benzofuranyl)methane : The above ester (0.5 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (20%; 10 ml.) for 1 hr. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from dil. alcohol in white small needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 317°. (Found : C, 67.59; H, 3.92. $C_{19}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 67.86; H, 3.57%).

Bi(5-benzofuranyl)methane : The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with copper powder (0.2 g.) in quinoline (15 ml.) for half an hour and the solution filtered. Conc. hydrochloric acid was added to the filtrate. The separated product was crystallised from petroleum ether in brown shining leaflets (0.1 g.), m.p. 75–76°. (Found : C, 82.24; H, 5.03. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 82.23; H, 4.84%).

Bi(3-Carboxy-6-coumarinyl) methane : 3,3'-Diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxy diphenyl methane (0.5 g.) was mixed with diethyl malonate (1 ml.) and piperidine (4 drops). The reaction mixture was kept for 48 hr. at room temperature and then washed with alcohol and dil. hydrochloric acid. The product was crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 178°. (Found : C, 66.77; H, 4.48. $C_{25}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 66.96; H, 4.46%).

Bi(3-carboxy-6-coumarinyl)methane : The above ester (0.5 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (20 ml.; 20%) for 5 hr. The product obtained on acidification with hydrochloric acid was crystallised from nitrobenzene in amorphous powder (0.3 g.), m.p. 306°. (Found : C, 64.04; H, 3.13. $C_{21}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 64.29; H, 3.06%).

Bi(6-coumarinyl)methane : The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with copper powder (0.2 g.) in quinoline (10 ml.) for half an hour and the reaction mixture worked up as before. The decarboxylated product was crystallised from dil. alcohol in amorphous powder (0.2 g.), m.p. 203–4°. (Found : C, 75.36; H, 4.42. $C_{29}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.98; H, 3.95%).

The same coumarin was obtained when 3,3'-diformyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane (0.5 g.) was refluxed with fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) for 12 hr. in oil bath at 180–90° and the reaction mixture was poured into water. M.P. and mixed m.p. with the above coumarin was 203°.

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